

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

DIABETES FOOT ULCER¹Tanuja M. Langote, ²Sakshi S Mahalle, ³Sarvesh T Lawange, ⁴Vinayak A.Katekar,
⁵Dr.Swati P .Deshmukh¹Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.²Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.³Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.⁴Department of Quality Assurance, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India⁵Department of Pharmacology, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.**Abstract:**

Diabetes mellitus is disorder of abnormal high blood glucose levels i.e. hyperglycemia Acc⁺⁺ who in 2016, 422 million adults suffered from diabetes mellitus, types "insulin depended diabetes mellitus" or "Juvenile diabetes mellitus" {NIDDM} or "adult onset diabetes" and gestational diabetes it occurs during pregnancy. Effective management of diabetes mellitus can decreased the severity of disease by preventing amputations and mortality. blood sugar control, wound debridement and advanced dressings is part of management the main symptoms of diabetes foot ulcer is hyperglycemia, increased fluid intake, blurred vision, change in energy metabolism, increased urine production and hyperglycemia. The uncontrolled diabetes mellitus caused diabetes

Keywords:- NIDDM, Gestational diabetes, Hyperglycemia, Necrotic Tissue, Retinopathy, Macrophages, Cytokine Effect.

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Please cite this article in press Sarvesh T Lawange et al., *Diabetes Foot Ulcer*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (02).

INTRODUCTION:

According to WHO in 2016 442 million adults suffered from diabetes Mellitus. This is generally seen on foot & a major complication of the disease is loss of lower limbs. The other complication is during the early stage of the disease peripheral vascular disease occurs or seen in majority & tissue loss in advanced stage diabetic foot.

Ulcer has other symptoms like hyperkeratosis, dry skin, lack of sensitivity, peripheral neuropathy, motor neuropathy etc. Many people go for amputation which is a very painful therapy. The diabetic ulcer also causes diabetes Mellitus & leads to DFU.

Diabetic foot ulcer etiology: -

The radiology of diabetic foot ulcers are improper foot care, foot deformities, poor glycemic control, poor quality of shoes, poor hygiene.

1. Increase blood sugar level:-

Increase glycemia or sugar level in blood stiffens the arteries resulting in decreased blood & oxygen to the body.

2. Inflammation: -

It occurs due to injury to tissue due to neuropathic, Macrophage & mast cells causing inflammation. The cytokine effect the inflammation response. Pro-inflammatory cytokines are produced by activating Macrophages and involved in regulating inflammation reaction.

3. Peripheral Neuropathy / Nerve damage:-

It occurs when nerves located outside of brain & spinal cord are damaged. It occurs due to diabetes, pain and diabetes reduced supply of oxygen and nutrients to the body.

4. Infection: -

It is increased due to exposure to the environment and it may require amputation.

Sign & symptoms

Common signs & symptoms of diabetic wound are chronic pain.

*Signs of inflammation- swelling, redness, heat, pain & loss of functions.

*Signs of infection - pus, drainage, bad odor, dead tissue, redness, pus.

- "Drainage or blood in shoes or socks.

-large callus or cracked heels

-Large term high blood, sugar can cause a type of never dagger

-Diabetes can also affect blood flow to leg and feet.

-This condition causes arteries to become narrow or block.

-Darkened skin on the affected area.

-Diminished ability to sense hot or cold.

-Loss of hair in the area.

-Numbness.

Treatment and cure of diseases.

Glycemic control:- Increasing evidence has shown that intensive glycemic control delays the onset and slows the progression of diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy in patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus.

Pharmacological therapy: -

Individualized patient education, improved diabetes knowledge and self-management activities have improved medication adherence to oral diabetic medications in Case Controlled trial.

Improving Vascularization: -

Revascularization of occluded ischemic legs results in increased perfusion.

Offloading

Further pressure reducing and redistribution of weight bearing load over an increased area of the foot can be achieved.

Offloading strategies**Wound dressing: -**

It is an external protection and barrier to external force and contaminants while promoting absorption of exudate around the wound site. There were a variety of dressings available along with increasingly advanced methods of promoting wound healing.

Maggot therapy :-

Use of maggot therapy primarily functions by removing dead necrotic tissue leaving healthy granulation tissue on the wound bed.

Negative pressure wound therapy: -

Target negative pressure wound therapy is another increasingly common method used in the management of diabetic foot ulcers.

Prevention of infection.

- Taking the pressure off the area. Called offloading
- Removing dead skin and tissue. Called "debridement"
- Managing blood glucose and other health problems.

REFERENCES:

- 1) American Diabetes Association (2004) physical Activity / Exercise and diabetes care 27:558-562
- 2) Boyko · E.J. Ahroni. JH. Stensel V, foresberg, R.C. Davignon, D.R. Smith D. G (1999) A prospective Study of Risk factors for diabetic Foot ulcers. Diabetic Care 22:1036-1042

- 3) Boulton AJM. (1996). The pathogenesis of diabetic foot problems : an overview. *Diabet med*, 8: 5/12-S16.
- 4) Abetz L, Sutton M, Brady L, (2002) The diabetic foot ulcer scale: a Quality of life instrument for use in clinical trials. *Pract Diab Int* 19: 167-175.
- 5) Brownrigg JR, Davey J, Holt PJ (2012) The association of ulceration of The foot with cardiovascular and all-cause mortality in patients with Diabetes: a meta-analysis. *Diabetologia* 55(11): 2906-2912.
- 6) Brem H, Balledux J, Bloom T, Kerstein MD, Hollier L (2000) Healing of Diabetic foot ulcers and pressure ulcers with human skin equivalent: a New paradigm in wound healing. *Arch Surg* 135(6): 627-634.
- 7) Bennett SP, Griffiths GD, Schor AM, Leese GP, Schor SL (2003) Growth Factors in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers. *Br J Surg* 90(2): 133- 146.
- 8) Shahbazian H, Yazdanpanah L, Latifi SM. Risk assessment of patients with diabetes for foot ulcers according to risk classification consensus of International Working Group on Diabetic Foot (IWGDF) *Pak J Med Sci.* 2013;29:730–734.
- 9) Dutta P, Bhansali A, Mittal BR, Singh B, Masoodi SR (2006) Instant 99mTc-ciprofloxacin scintigraphy for the diagnosis of osteomyelitis in The diabetic foot. *Foot Ankle Int* 27(9): 716-722.
- 10) National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (2011) Diabetic Foot problems: inpatient management of diabetic foot problems. Clinical guide- line 119. NICE, London, UK. Rathur HM, Boulton AJM (2007) The diabetic foot. *Clin Dermatol* 25:109-120.
- 11). Young MJ, McCardle JE, Randall LE (2008) Improved survival of Diabetic foot ulcer patients 1995-2008: possible impact of aggressive Cardiovascular risk management. *Diabetes Care* 31(11): 2143-2147.
12. Hinchcliffe RJ, Andros G, Apelqvist J M. Kumhar, T. Saini, and N. Dara, “Foot wear and footcare knowledge—an independent
- 13) P. N. Nyamu, C. F. Otieno, E. O. Amayo, and S. O. McLigeyo, “Risk factors and prevalence Of diabetic foot ulcers at Kenyatta National Hospital, Nairobi,” *East African Medical Journal*, vol. 80, no. 1, 2003.
- 14) F. Al-Maskari and M. El-Sadig, “Prevalence of risk factors for diabetic foot Complications,” *BMC Family Practice*, vol. 8, p. 59, 2007.
- 15) S Das, A concise Textbook of surgery, Published by Dr. S. Das, 6th edition, Pg 162, Pp 1226.
- 16) S Das, A concise Textbook of surgery, Published by Dr. S. Das, 6th edition, Pg 134, Pp 1226.
- 17) S Das, A concise Textbook of surgery, Published by Dr. S. Das, 6th edition, Pg 373, Pp 1226.
- 18) S Das, A concise Textbook of surgery, Published by Dr. S. Das, 6th edition, Pg 235, Pp (2012) A systematic review of The effectiveness of revascularisation of the ulcerated foot in patients With diabetes and peripheral arterial disease. *Diabetes Metab Res Rev* 28(Suppl1)79 2171226
American Diabetes Association (2004) Physical Activity/Exercise and Diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 27: S58-S62.
- 19) Boyko, E.J., Ahroni, J.H., Stensel, V, Forsberg, R.C., Davignon, D.R., Smith, D.G. (1999) A Prospective study of risk factors for diabetic foot Ulcer. *Diabetes Care*, 22:1036–1042.
- 20) American Diabetes Association. Consensus Development Conference on Diabetic Foot Wound Care, Boston, Massachusetts. American Diabetes Association. *Diabetes Care* 1999, 22, 1354–1360.
- 21) Wu, S.C.; Crews, R.T.; Armstrong, D.G. The pivotal role of offloading in the management of neuropathic foot Ulceration. *Curr. Diabetes Rep.* 2005, 5, 423–429. [CrossRef]
- 22) Lavery, L.A.; Vela, S.A.; Lavery, D.C.; Quebedeaux, T.L. Reducing dynamic foot pressures in high-risk diabetic Subjects with foot ulcerations: A comparison of treatments. *Diabetes Care* 1996, 19, 818–821. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- 23) Abdulrazak, A.; Bitar, Z.I.; Al-Shamali, A.A.; Mobasher, L.A. Bacteriological study of diabetic foot infections. *J. Diabetes Complicat.* 2005, 19, 138–141. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- 24) Ho, T.K.; Leigh, R.D.; Tsui, J. Diabetic foot disease and oedema. *Br. J. Diabetes Vasc. Disease* 2013, 13, 45–50. [CrossRef]
- 24) Bowering, C.K. Use of layered compression bandages in diabetic patients. Experience in patients with lower Leg ulceration, peripheral edema, and features of venous and arterial disease. *Adv. Wound Care* 1998, 11, 129–135. [PubMed]
- 26) Thomas, S. Compression Bandaging in the Treatment of Venous Leg Ulcers. Available online: <http://www.worldwidewounds.com/1997/september/Thomas-Bandaging/bandage-paper.html> (accessed on 20 July 2015).
- 27) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. National Diabetes Statistics Report: Estimates of Diabetes and Its Burden in the United States; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services: Atlanta, GA, USA, 2014.
- 28) Boulton, A.J.M.; Malik, R.A.; Arezzo, J.C.; Sosenko, J.M. Diabetic somatic neuropathies:

- Technical review. *Diabetes Care* 2004, 27, 1458–1486. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- 29) Reiber, G.E.; Vileikyte, L.; Boyko, E.J.; Aguila, M.; Smith, D.G.; Lavery, L.A.; Boulton, A.J. Causal pathways For incident lower-extremity ulcers in patients with diabetes from two settings. *Diabetes Care* 1999, 22,157–162. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- 30) Boulton, A.J.M.; Armstrong, D.G.; Albert, S.F.; Frykberg, R.G.; Hellman, R.; Kirkman, M.S.; Lavery, L.A.; Lemaster, J.W.; Mills, J.L., Sr.; Mueller, M.J.; et al. Comprehensive foot examination and risk assessment: A report of the task force of the foot care interest group of the American Diabetes Association, with Endorsement by the American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists. *Diabetes Care* 2008, 31, 1679–1685. [CrossRef] [PubMed]